

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Magumise****FIRST NAME: Dakarayi Yvorne****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR'S LAST NAME: Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2024,7-12)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2024, 15-23)
3. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024,34-39)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2024,40-42)
6. Chicago Manual Style (EUCLID 2024,43-57)

Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLUD 2024,58-62)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING (DOCTORATE)

1) INTRODUCTION

It has been a long time since my last experience with academics. My last encounter with dedicated learning was in 2022 when I studied a taught program. It was so much joy and appreciation to be accepted by the EUCLID University. On being granted access to the coursework, my journey started. I started on a long, winding road due to not following instructions and applying all the information and learning handles offered. This whole process was further complicated by my nominal computer skills and reduced study time because of my workload at my workplace. I am so grateful for the student network that the EUCLID University formed and my course instructor, Professor Gulma, who was able to assist and give me directions. Now, my journey has begun. I started with systematic reading. The first item I read and re-read was the Orientation PDF, which unpacked the student's expectations. My first encounter with the videos was not helpful at first as I did not pay attention. My fellow students encouraged me to pay attention and to replay several times. Finally, I succeeded in downloading the Zotero and Grammarly applications

(Vimeo, n.d.). The key reading material ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack (Period 1), written by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck and Doctor Kabiru Gulma, has been extremely helpful to me as I work through Period 1. I have enjoyed learning new concepts, especially essay writing and Latin Abbreviations and expressions. The tutorial given by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck on using the Response Paper (RP) template has given me the courage to attempt to write my RP paper. At this point, it is beginning to make sense of what I am doing, and the direction is taking shape. I assume that some of us are laggards.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The skill of essay writing is one that every academic needs to master for the expression and display of their work. Chapter I, in ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack (Period 1) elaborates on essay writing. This chapter aims to give the student an overview of the basics of essay writing, the steps of writing, and the general rules (EUCLID 2024, 6). Developing a relevant and novel topic is among the most difficult things in academic research and writing. In this chapter, I learned how to research a topic by creating a reading list of credible academic materials, for example, journals, books, periodicals, dissertations, etc (EUCLID 2024, 7). Planning, preparation, time management, and personal organisation were suggested to overcome procrastination.

There are important questions to answer when you are researching a topic and the information to write in an essay. These questions include capturing the information you already know about the subject and the resources you need to read to enhance your knowledge of the subject to develop a thesis and answer questions. The aspects of creative and critical thinking were a phenomenon that was intriguing to me since I had not done written work in a long time. I was taught the art of organising my thoughts by writing a plan. I am implementing this as I write my Response Paper 1.

Once the resources have been put together, there is a need for copious note-taking, including citing the references, to avoid plagiarism. The selected information is then used to prepare a draft, which is used to write the essay. Essay writing is structured into three basic components: the introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2024, 10). It is interesting to know that you write the introduction to the essay after the body. I have used United Kingdom (UK) English for my particular writing. I appreciate Grammarly's assistance with grammar. I would like to conclude the matter of essay writing by concluding that one should never introduce new material, ideas, and information in conclusion (EUCLID 2024, 10).

3) PUNCTUATIONS

According to EUCLID (2024, 16), the general rule for punctuation is to “Use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence.”

In this chapter, I was introduced to various punctuation markers, their significance, and their application in writing. It is noted that a punctuation mark's application or

omission changes a sentence's meaning. Punctuation marks have to be used correctly at all times and to use the correct one.

Various punctuation marks that were used are apostrophes, brackets, bullet points, colons and semicolons, commas, dashes and hyphens, ellipses, full stops, exclamation, questions, and quotation marks, as discussed in EUCLID (2024,16). The ellipsis is the one that I am quite unfamiliar with. It was interesting to learn that it indicates missing text from a quote or the end of a clause (EUCLID 2024, 22).

I used to think that comma-separated words and sentences, especially where one would speak and not want to put a full stop but continue with the speech. I have learned that there is what is called 'comma splicing', i.e., adding a comma after adverbial phrases like nevertheless, therefore, and however (EUCLID 2024,19).

Constant use of punctuation marks will certainly improve with application. Mastering punctuation certainly improves grammar, bringing my writing to the next level.

4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

Being educated under a British system and curriculum, my natural inclination would be to use British English. I was surprised that American English is more popular and dominates the global arena than British English. As I would have thought otherwise since the English originated from the British. However, the two variants are said to be similar rather than different when it comes to educated or scientific English, as observed in pronunciation and common spellings.

I noticed that the authors emphasised that the two variants cannot be used interchangeably; one should choose between the two. American and British English have not remained static but have been dynamic in growth as they have included new words derived from cultural and technological changes, for example, nerd, blogging, and up/downloading.

5) PLAGIARISM

The act of plagiarism is defined by (EUCLID 2024, 34) as a failure by a writer to give credit to the author of the source of information that they are using. According to the Oxford Dictionary, plagiarism is defined as 'The action or practice of taking someone else's work, idea, etc., and passing it off as one's own; literary theft' (Oxford University Press 2025). I have learned that plagiarism is unethical and wrong, is as good as stealing and has legal consequences (EUCLID 2024, 34). I notice that the authors emphasise citing the original author when using any quote, paraphrase, statistic/data, or visuals from other sources (EUCLID 2024, 35). Search engines are used to assist with citing. I have used Zotero as my search engine. I had to learn to re-learn after a long period. The cited work is listed as a reference or a bibliography at the bottom of the written work. There are other ways that I have learned to avoid direct copying, such as, paraphrasing. Paraphrasing is

writing the ideas and information of the author in your own words and style. However, I have also learned when not to cite, considering that we cannot cite everything in the written document.

6) STYLE GUIDE

According to EUCLID (2024), a style guide is a method and rules an author follows to achieve a high level of consistency. This allows the written work to be coherent and consistent. Here at EUCLID, we are encouraged to use Chicago Rules (Turabian). I have learned that style guides assist in more than just punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary but include other aspects, as stated in the coursepack. In my writings this is the first time I have been introduced to a style guide, and I have found it most helpful in giving my work structure.

A style guide is an essential tool for every writer as it standardises the work, making it more acceptable to readers and publishers. I have found it easier to write the RP following the style guide given by the coursepack. Initially, it felt like a daunting task even to start writing the essay.

7) CMS CRIB SHEET

The Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) Crib Sheet documents the way of using the Chicago Style when formatting books, research papers, theses and dissertations. As I write this report, I am learning to apply all the rules of the Chicago Style. Some aspects are quite new and fascinating, such as the use of compound words and numbers. The Chicago Page Formatting has challenged me; my skills will improve with practice.

8) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

I have learned that some abbreviations we commonly use are derived from Latin, although they are now used in the daily English language. Popular examples would be, e.g. (*exempli gratia*), etc. (*et cetera*), i.e. (*id est*) the list goes on. According to EUCLID 2024, Latin abbreviations are appropriate in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing. However, in business, formal and technical writing, it is suggested to use English abbreviations as these are commonly understood by most readers. It was emphasised that the best way to create content is to use the principle of 'Plain language' for better communication (Laurent Cleenewerck, Kabiru Gulma 2024)

9) CONCLUSION

As the old English adage says, "The journey of a thousand miles begins with a single step." This has been a tantamount start for me. I am glad that I have started the

learning process, and I have enjoyed learning new things and, in the process, improving my writing and computer skills. I have acquainted myself with punctuation, style guide and Latin. Each building block in the course pack has given me new and deep insights into the area of writing. I am looking forward to the next level.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 5th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

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